

IN REPETITION AND REINFORCEMENT LESSONS USING ELEMENTS OF THE STEAM EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM TECHNOLOGY

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Abstract: In this article, the organization of repetition and reinforcement lessons in general education schools based on interactive methods, the use of elements of the STEAM educational system technology in such lessons, the connection of theoretical knowledge with practice, interdisciplinarity, students' logical, creative, creative, issues such as improving critical thinking, working in cooperation, and communication skills are highlighted.

Keywords: STEAM educational system technology elements, creative thinking, logical, critical thinking and problem solving skills, creative thinking.

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, increasing the quality and efficiency of the educational system in our country, forming modern knowledge and skills in students and young people, close cooperation and integration between educational systems and the field of science, education world-class reforms are being implemented to ensure continuity. In the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 29, 2019 "On approval of the concept of development of the public education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030" No. formation of effective motivation and development of abilities to choose a profession, independent planning of professional growth, acquisition of modern professions; "Introducing general education programs and new state standards that meet the requirements of the modern innovative economy, taking into account the special emphasis on the development of STEAM subjects and critical thinking, independent search for information, analytical competencies and skills" is one of the main requirements for today's education. The above-mentioned tasks can be put into practice in properly organized repetition and reinforcement lessons based on various interactive methods in the subject of the mother tongue.

World education experts say that STEAM education helps students develop the following skills.

1. Think and take risks.
2. Engage in meaningful learning activities.
3. Become resilient problem solvers.
4. Embrace and value cooperation.
5. Work through the creative process.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS (ЛИТЕРАТУРА И МЕТОДОЛОГИЯ / METHODS)

Our study of various literature on the field shows that in STEAM technology, attention is paid to the combination of theoretical and practical knowledge, in such an educational environment, children learn to use their acquired knowledge immediately: to know, to think, to work independently, they get a strong motivation for creativity. This education directs

children to conduct experiments, build models, put forward ideas, and put theory into practice.

The STEAM program develops critical and analytical thinking skills necessary for children to quickly find optimal solutions to the difficulties and problems they face in their daily lives, to correctly analyze various situations. STEAM program is distinguished by active communication and teamwork. A free environment is created for the participant of the process to express his opinion and engage in debate during the dialogue. They learn to speak and present. If children always actively participate in classes with the teacher and classmates, they will remember information well, will have the opportunity to effectively combine theoretical knowledge and practical skills. Students' creativity will be developed. It will be a solid foundation for the training of highly qualified, up-to-date personnel. Since such activities are very dynamic and interesting, children do not get bored and do not notice how time has passed.

As a result of our research, it became clear that the tasks given in the reinforcement lessons in the mother tongue textbooks are very similar in terms of meaning and content. Some of these assignments are aimed at developing students' "speaking" and "writing" skills. In particular, the 5th grade native language textbook of general secondary schools.

In the 2nd task of the "Lesson 99. Reinforcement" lesson, the student should copy the text, underline the terms, state your conclusion about the text, in the 3rd task, write down the terms related to a profession, science, internet and economy, problem, browser, product, sewing machine, buy, randa, equation, oxygen, product, hydrosphere, site should make oral sentences.

Task 4. Divide into groups. Within five minutes, write words about the 1st group of professions and the 2nd group of sciences. The group that writes the fastest and most is the winner.

Task 5. Homework. Create a text of 10-12 sentences about the profession of one of your relatives. In this textbook "Lesson 95. Exercise 336. Homework on the topic "Terms related to exact sciences". Write 10 terms related to mathematics and find out their explanations. "Lesson 96. "Terms related to social and humanitarian sciences" topic "Assignment. Read the text. Find and copy the historical terms. Exercise 339, "Lesson 97. Work on text and vocabulary" and exercises 340-341 exactly repeated each other.

DISCUSSION (ОБСУЖДЕНИЕ)

A modern student, who is well aware of advanced technologies and its innovations, may get bored with such assignments and lose motivation to learn science.

"Achieving a guaranteed result is reflected in the clearly set goal of the modern lesson, the amount of knowledge completed in each studied topic is assumed, and this knowledge is a logical continuation of the previous knowledge, and based on what interactive methods, students are taught (Students) must reflect the guidelines for independent knowledge acquisition. For this: - the teacher teaches the student the ways of independent learning;

- it is important for the student to be able to analyze analytically, to make comparative descriptions, to draw inductive and deductive conclusions, to be able to summarize the acquired evidence into a system and to apply it in practice.

RESULTS (РЕЗУЛЬТАТЫ)

So, reinforcement lessons can be organized based on the STEAM approach as follows. At the beginning of the lesson, students are divided into small groups. Educational tools necessary

for the presentation are provided: markers, watman paper, etc. Answers are presented by small groups: opinions are explained, proved. It is controlled that each member of the group is active.

Teacher: Dear students. In the past trainings, we got acquainted with terms related to scientific, professional, economic, Internet-specific, specific and social-humanities sciences. We will consolidate our knowledge in today's lesson.

Task 1. Children, watch the schedule carefully.

Q: Which of the following subjects to occupy jewelry

Definitely important	May need	Not important

Students write their thoughts to the table. They are presented.

Teacher's response:

Dear children. In the very fast-growing season, you will definitely help you, of course, your solid knowledge, which you receive from different subjects. As you can see in the table above, you should have competitive, hand flower jeweler and skills in various fronts.

1. The science of chemistry is the correct use of different metals: interaction, dissatisfaction, thawing, etc.
2. Termomation - Only if the size of different items is, the weight of the different objects is high.
3. The worker should skillfully draw the picture, painting of your belongings you want to make things.
4. Computer graphics is to create jewelry, creating new brands on a computer, to get acquainted with world-jewelry products.
5. Consent to provide detailed information on their products to sell jewelry products. The basis of any business is advertising. The ability to use language units ensures the success of the product advertising. The information provided by humans, internet networks and the outside - purchases the goods needed for daily lives from advertising from advertising.
6. We know how to speak with collaboration - buyer, bookcare, and guilty, skillfully find the way from different situations.
7. Chetics - Every entrepreneur will go to world markets dreams. The guarantee of success in establishing joint ventures with foreign partners and signing transactions is the key to success.

8.Bounds - If the jeweler wants to act as a minor business, it is not without the bene fit of knowing various accounting calculations. Of course, the industry specialists will be involved. But primary knowledge only brings us beneficial.

Task 2. Backers, what aspects do you think are important in choosing a profession? Explace your opinion in percentage

Personal ability	
Parent	
Love to occupation	
Financial opportunities	

URreport Youth Platform, which is the special project of UNICEF . He conducted a survey of young people. More than 6,600,000 Uzbek youths took part in it. According to respondents, the following 4 factors will affect the 4th choice:

1. Personal ability (34%);
2. Love for profession (20%);
3. Financial capabilities (20%)
4. There is the decision to do (11%).

82% of the participants believe that the profession should be organized by the government.

Dear children. We have strengthened the topics of terms in our class. The future professions have learned that it is necessary to master various disciplines in each profession. Decrees, state programs, decisions are signed, state programs, decisions, employment, employment, employment, especially young businessmen by our President and government. You also master the future of the future by age knowledge. Retomity - serve our Motherland, honestly, smiled, dedicated to our nationality, even though you are a profession, our nation!

CONCLUSION (ЗАКЛЮЧЕНИЕ)

As a result of the application of Steam software items in repetition and strengthening lessons

- Actual communication and organization of personal opinions is developed skills to justify;
- Enriches the learning process, increases the desire to lose science;
- Cognitive (expansion of the diversity of knowledge, knowing Information is provided;
- Detailed study, perception, perception, comparison of various information within the subject develops the concection of the optimal option;
- The knowledge necessary for students to prepare for independent life;
- Behind different groups, the fact that is divided by a positive, friendly relationship, develops nutrient problems and problems in solving life difficulties and problems.

During the talks period, a free environment will be created to state its opinion and to discuss its opinion. They learn to speak and present. If children are always actively involved in training and their classmates, they will be able to make the information well, and the creativity of giving theoretical knowledge is developed.

Students will strengthen the past lesson. They can apply the terms on scientific, vocational, economic, Internet, clear and social sciences in practice. However, many new and interesting information will have many new and interesting information. To become modern professionals and competitive frames, they consider the fullover of different subjects. To think of the opinion of others, to understand the opinion of others, and to make a logical, crematic and systemic and systematic thinking, critical creative and systemic thinking, creating logical,

crucial, creative and systematic thinking. The necessary conditions will be created for the display of intellecting and spiritual abilities and the formation of a spiritually harmonious person.

The requirements of various, including linguistic competence of linguistic tongue, are performed on a native language. The reader absorbs new words and phrases, it can explain the meaning of words; He can apply the contents of the learned expression properly and in written speech.

Hence, the use of elements of Steam education system technology in the repetition and strengthening lessons is practical in training of elements of STEMIKAL Self-Care Rehabilitation, Fulfillment of the requirements for modern education.

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